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Research Article

**MINIMIZATION OF RISKS AND THREATS IN THE SYSTEM
OF ECONOMIC SECURITY AT THE MESO-LEVEL****Elena Kushch¹, Oksana Takhumova², Elena Drannikova³, Ekaterina Alehina⁴,
Olga Malinina⁴**¹North-Caucasus Federal University, Pushkin str., 1, Stavropol 355009, Russia²Kuban State Agrarian University named after I.T. Trubilin, 13 Kalinina str., Krasnodar 350044, Russia, ³MIREA - Russian Technological University, branch in Stavropol, Kulakova Avenue, 8,Stavropol 355000, Russia, ⁴Don State Technical University, Institute of Service and Entrepreneurship (branch), Shevchenko str., 147, Rostov Region, Shakhty 346500, Russia.**Article Received:** December 2018 **Accepted:** February 2019 **Published:** March 2019**Abstract:**

This article presents clarified the criteria for threats to the economic security of the regions as a whole and separately for the organization. The risks of reducing the steady growth of economic indicators at the micro level are identified. Presented recommendations to improve the economic condition of the business entity. The results of the analysis can be used in the development and implementation of the economic security system of Russian companies.

Keywords: *economic security, state, threats, organization, ways to ensure economic growth, efficiency.***Corresponding author:****Elena Kushch,**

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INTRODUCTION:

In the period of technological development of modern society, many countries have a great need to improve the level of economic security, as in the context of globalization there are many adverse events that threaten economic stability, both for individual organizations and for the state as a whole. The need to ensure economic security is the prevention of possible and real economic hazards that may threaten the socio-economic stability of a country and certain areas of activity [4]. From a theoretical point of view, this is a complex of factors ensuring the independence of the market economic system, the sustainability of development, and continuous reproduction. The main goal, in turn, is to ensure the stable financial development of the state or organization in the interests of meeting social and financial needs [6-9].

The direction of research is of particular interest from a scientific and practical point of view. This is due to the dynamic trends in the development of economic relations in the market system and modern society. Options for threats to economic security at the meso level are very diverse. In order to optimize work in the field of protection of key assets and processes of financial and economic activities of entities, it is necessary to timely identify the most negative factors susceptible to negative phenomena that are carriers of the highest possible level of risk.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

Threats to the economic security of an economic entity are determined on the basis of an assessment of economic security, which can be assessed using the various criteria presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Criteria for assessing the economic security of the enterprise

No	Criterion	Characteristic
1.	Organizational	It assumes the preservation of the company itself and its organizational integrity, the normal functioning of the main divisions. The main structural elements of the organization (production department, supply department, marketing department, financial department or accounting department) carry out all without exception the functions that allow to achieve the main goal of the organization.
2.	Legal	It assumes the constant provision of compliance of the organization's work with current legislation, which is manifested in the absence of complaints from law enforcement agencies to the organization. In addition, there are no losses from transactions with external partners due to violation of current legislation. This is guaranteed by legal expertise of all executed transactions and transactions concluded by agreements.
3.	Informational	Security can be assessed as ensuring the state of security of internal secret data from loss or disclosure in various configurations.
4.	Economic	This aspect is expressed in sustainable or with a tendency to growth of key financial and economic indicators of the organization. They reflect the general results of ensuring security from the organizational, legal, informational and economic sides.

As one of the options for identifying business risks, you can apply, for example, a multifactorial model.

Figure 1: Multifactor model of identification of business risks

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

There are various types of economic security: at the level of the region and the organization, and also highlight the economic security of a citizen or entrepreneur. In order to provide the economic security of the state, region, industry, organization, it is necessary to single out those real and possible destructive security requirements with various manifestations that act as probable threats. Considering the threats to the economic security of the country, it should be noted that this, in turn, is the probability of harming the nation's economy as a whole and its sectors, the country's financial and credit policy, the likelihood of violation of the socio-economic sustainability of the state and the financial situation of the individual [2].

The existing imbalances in the texture of the economy are a significant factor in ensuring economic security, which are associated with low competitiveness of products, the outflow of a significant part of financial resources from the Russian economy, and the decline in business activity of many businesses in the business sector.

Speaking about the economic security of the country, allocate external and internal threats. The external threats include: the advantage of raw materials in the export structure; the dependence of the country's economy on world prices; increase in external debt; poor development of information and transport infrastructure; underdeveloped transport

infrastructure, which deals with the maintenance of export-import operations.

The internal conditions that pose a danger to the economic security of the state include: the low competitiveness of the domestic economy, which is caused by the backwardness of the scientific and technological base of many industries, the considerable resource intensity and energy intensity; a high degree of monopolization of the economy; high inflation; weak development and stability of many infrastructure facilities.

Currently, the number of threats is increasing, economic security has the ability to shake, not only under the influence of economic, but also military and political factors. This is peculiar to the policies of Western states in comparison with other, underdeveloped countries in economic and military terms. The main means of prevention, prevention and elimination of hazards are the intensive work of government bodies at all levels, and the implementation of a set of measures to prevent and counter threats to economic security must be provided with state funding.

In matters of ensuring stable economic development, the most interesting research is on organization. The economic security of a company is understood as the state of protection of the basic interests of an individual subject from internal and external threats, which is formed by managers and employees through the implementation of economic, legal, engineering,

organizational and socio-psychological measures. [3]
To ensure the economic security of the organization decided to allocate the following tasks:

- 1) Identify the composition and nature of the threats to the economic security of the enterprise;
- 2) Assess the expected damage from the effects of threats to the economic security of an economic entity;
- 3) Distribute threats to economic security;
- 4) To form and select options for strategies to ensure the economic security of the enterprise;
- 5) Identify and implement specific measures to ensure the economic security of the enterprise [1].

To develop practical recommendations we will focus on the economic assessment of the criteria for the development of a small business organization in one of the developed regions of the country, the Krasnodar Territory. LIVAD LLC was selected as the company under consideration. On June 25, 2002, the Registration Chamber of the Krasnodar City Administration was selected. The legal address is Krasnodar Region, Krasnodar Territory, Krasnodar City, Babushkina Street, 252. The purpose of the activity is economic activity, which is aimed at making a profit and meeting the social and economic

needs of the participants and members of the workforce of the organization in question.

The organization offers a wide range of products for the meat and dairy and confectionery industries. The main activity is the wholesale of powdered milk, whey powder, butter, flour, sugar and buckwheat. Also, the organization rents 600 sq.m. warehouses for storage of products. As is known, threats to the economic security of a company are determined on the basis of an assessment of economic security, we calculate and analyze general threats. Based on the above results, it can be concluded that the organization has a high turnover rate (27.3-33.3%) over the past few years, the likely reason for this may be the lack of growth factors, or the proposed more favorable conditions for staff. Also, the turnover ratio of working capital in 2016 decreased significantly, which may indicate excessive accumulation of working capital of the enterprise. The indicator of the duration of turnover in 2016 increased by 148 days, which indicates an increase in the average residence time of current assets in the process of circulation. Profitability indicator of sales in LLC LIVAD is below the norm.

Table 2: Threats to the organization's economic security

Indicator	2015	2016	2017
Staff turnover rate	0,333	0,3	0,273
Labor productivity, thousand rubles	13098	8473	4182
The turnover ratio of working capital	6,532	3,743	1,774
Duration of turnover of working capital, days	55	96	203
The rate of renewal of fixed assets	0,895	0,944	1,062
The depreciation of fixed assets	0,06	0,12	0,14
Coefficient of shelf life of fixed assets	0,94	0,88	0,86
Return on sales,%	0,9	2,8	2,1
Commercial profitability,%	0,125	0,622	2,549
Leverage ratio	0,613	0,708	0,635
Altman Z-scheme at the end of the year	5,591	4,163	2,835
Integral assessment of the financial sustainability of the organization, class	5	5	5

The norm of the financial leverage ratio is 1, and the significantly low value of the financial leverage ratio indicates a missed opportunity to use a lever of this type, therefore it is necessary to increase the return on equity by engaging borrowed funds. Grade 5 of the integral assessment of financial stability indicates the highest risk, non-solvency and insolvency of the enterprise.

One of the tools to provide economic security for the company is the formation of the organization of the

security service. The question of its formation arises in the period when the resolution on the organization of the company is adopted, depending on the preferred type of activity, the size of the goods to be manufactured, the annual turnover and income, the use of production secrets, the number of employees.

In Figure 2, we present an approximate structure of the organization's own security, which can be created to increase the security of its economic interests.

Figure 2: Structure of the organization's own security

Also, to increase the economic security of an organization, you can suggest using the following measures to eliminate threats:

- 1) Periodically carry out an analysis of financial and economic activities;
- 2) Regularly monitor the activities of the organization, including the implementation of plans for the sale of goods and profit in the company;
- 3) Identify stocks to increase the amount of the amount of profit and profitability;
- 4) Systematically study and analyze the laws of the Russian Federation and the regions, by-laws, as well as instructions and regulations, analyze and process the information received;
- 5) It is recommended to collect, process and analyze information about organizations that are interested in the work of the enterprise;
- 6) To study and analyze information about the proposed and actual partners of the enterprise, as well as how they behave in the market.
- 7) Collect and analyze information on criminal structures, identify agents of these structures within the enterprise.
- 8) To study and analyze information about competitors and how they work in the market and within the organization.

CONCLUSION:

Analyzing modern threats to the company's economic security, we can conclude that constant monitoring of the socio-economic, political, and technological conditions of the organization's operations is necessary to protect the economic interests of the business entity. The implementation of a productive economic security device at the meso-level needs adequate attention from the management to the organization's financial and economic activities, in terms of the amount of resources expended and a clear organization of production activities. Ensuring economic security at the present stage is a very complex process, which includes a certain number of

interrelated stages, the passage of which ensures the preservation of economic interests and the multiplication of the assets of the organization.

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